

Enabling Interconnected Science Workflows through an Adapter Approach

Jesse McGaha, Marshall McDonnell, Lance Drane, Seth Hitefield,
Gavin M. Wiggins, Gregory Cage,
Robert Smith, Mike Brim, Mark Abraham, Richard Archibald, and
Addi Malviya-Thakur

US-RSE Conference '23

What are “Interconnected Science Workflows”?

<https://www.ornl.gov/intersect>

Interconnected Science Ecosystem (INTERSECT) is an Oak Ridge National Laboratory Initiative to develop an open software framework for autonomous laboratories and self-driving autonomous experiments

INTERSECT Use Cases

Autonomous Microscopy

Autonomous Electric Grid Evaluations

Autonomous Chemistry Labs

Autonomous Additive Manufacturing

<https://www.ornl.gov/intersect>

Goals and Challenges of INTERSECT

- Goal
 - Develop software framework to create ecosystem of resources (instruments, compute, data, etc.) which can “talk” to each other
- Challenges:
 - Requires “control plane”, or communication, between heterogeneous resources in the ecosystem
 - How to make the resources understand each other?
 - How to integrate very different softwares together?
 - How to make them interoperable?

<https://www.ornl.gov/intersect>

A (possible) solution!

- Software engineering: use a design pattern!
 - **Modified version of “Adapter” pattern from object-oriented programming**
- INTERSECT Adapter: translate command and control communication in the scientific ecosystem to messages that are understood by other Adapters

<https://www.ornl.gov/intersect>

Examples of INTERSECT Adapter Use Cases

<https://www.ornl.gov/intersect>

Conclusions

<https://www.ornl.gov/intersect>

- INTERSECT software framework utilizes the concept of adapters to provide a standardized interface for resources to “talk”
- Adapter design pattern structures interconnecting the ecosystem, promotes interoperability, and aided in collaboration with domain science teams

Thanks!

Research sponsored by the Laboratory Directed Research and Development Program of Oak Ridge National Laboratory, managed by UT-Battelle, LLC, for the U. S. Department of Energy.